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Desulfurization of gas-oil onto Iraqi Using laboratory-improved clays

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ABSTRACT

Desulfurization of gas-oil was investigated. The adsorption desulfurization process was carried out on a highly efficient agent using various Clay Mineral (CM) (Attapulgate and Bentonite), which were brought from the western Iraqi desert. Desulfurization processes were investigated using applying three temperatures (400, 500 and 550 °C) and three kinds of catalysts: firstly CM only, secondly CM + (TiO₂ or ZnO or MoO₃) and thirdly Nano CM, by additive 5, 15 and 25% of minerals oxides both separately. TGA has shown the thermal stability of Clay and X-ray was used for measurement the conversion% of sulfurs, which were (0.95 to 0.47) using Attapulgate, (0.95 to 0.54) using Bentonite, (0.95 to 0.45) using Attapulgate + 25% TiO₂, (0.95 to 0.34) using Nano Bentonite + TiO₂ and, (0.95 to 0.29) using Nano Attapulgate + 25%TiO₂ which was the best. Desulfurization results. Which reteaching the good performance of the used catalyst. Gas Chromatography (GC) techniques are used to follow-up Dibenzothiophene (DBT) which is a compound in gas-oil.

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1. Introduction

Sulfur-containing compounds are one of the main contaminants in transportation fuels because through combustion they are converted to sulfur oxides (SO_x) that poison the noble-metal catalysts used in automobiles and contribute to acid rain and environmental pollution. Therefore, environmental regulations have become more and more stringent worldwide to limit the sulfur levels in transportation fuels [1].

The poor quality of crude oil currently can obviously result in the high sulfur contents of oil products, which can lead to corrosion, catalyst poisoning, and other negative consequences [2]. The removal of sulfur compounds from liquid fuels has become an important task in recent years, not only due to stringent environmental regulations but also for fuel cell applications. Sulfur content needs to be cut to

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below 0.1 ppm[3] because sulfur compounds in fuels are a major source of pollution and containing compounds such as thiophenes can poison catalysts used to remove the residue of hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides derived from combustion reactions [4].

Current technologies for the desulfurization of Crude Oil their Caustic washing method for oil desulfurization. Dry gas desulfurization method, Hydrodesulfurization (HDS), oxidative desulfurization (ODS) and bio desulfurization (BDS) [5]. Removal of organosulfur compounds by extraction or adsorption is economically viable and simple in operation. To meet the needs for producing clean fuels, decreasing the sulfur content of crude oil becomes an urgent task [6]. Commercial gasoline and diesel contain a large number of organic sulfur compounds with a concentration of 300 and 500 ppm (parts per million by weight). These sulfur compounds present in the fuel oils can cause serious environment pollution because they will be turned into SO_x species during combustion [7].

Sulfur compounds also result in the severe corrosion of reactors and equipment in the oil-processing step. Desulfurization of commercial fuels by selective adsorption has been reported as an alternative technology for the current HDS method. Yang and coworkers reported using zeolites for selective adsorption under ambient conditions for the desulfurization of commercial fuels [8]. Sun, L., Song, C.S., Mehdi, [9]. E. Torres-garcía,[10]. Kim: J. H., Song, C [11]. Wang, J. Mei, Z.J. [12]. However, the sulfur adsorption capacity depends on the composition of the fuel. Adsorptive removal of sulfur compounds from liquid commercial fuels has been widely investigated using various different adsorbents such as porous carbon materials, metal impregnated oxides, zeolite Y of various metal cation forms. Natural Clay, Micro and Nano-sized particles used as an adsorbent for the removal of organic compounds from oil such as organ-sulfurs. Nano Clay are extensively studied as new adsorbents with large surface area and small diffusion resistance for the separation and removal of chemical species. Different types of Clay minerals using as adsorbents.

Adsorption desulfurization is a new and highly efficient method to remove sulfur compounds from transportation fuels. In addition, adsorption desulfurization can be accomplished at relatively lower pressure and temperature even at ambient conditions [13].

The objective of the present investigation is to develop an improved process for the desulfurization of Gas-oil, using natural Clay as a catalyst of adsorbent and also activated that was impregnated with TiO₂, ZnO, and MoO₃. And examine its activity for adsorption desulfurization and the present study also reports the effect of metal salts on the adsorbent capacity. The efficiency of Nanocatalyst for adsorption process has been studied.

2. Materials and Methodology

2.1 Materials:

Diesel oil was collected locally from the Baiji refinery. The main physical properties of diesel oil are shown in Table.1. Clay Minerals (Bentonite - B, Attapulgite - A) collected from the Rutba area / Iraq. Table.2. Shown the components of Clay.

Table.1. Physical properties of Gas-oil (Baiji)

Test	Method	Specification
sp. gravity/ 15.6 °c	d-1298	0.84 max
a.p.i gravity	—	37.0 min
Colour astm	d-1500	2.0 max
Flash point (p.m) °c	d-93	54.0 min
Viscosity/40 °c	d-445	5.0 max
Pour point / °c	d-97	-9.0 max
Sulfur content wt%	d-1266	1.2 max - 0.75 min
Cetane index calculated	d-976	53.0 min
Diesel index	ip-21	55.0 min

Table.2. Constituent oxides of Clays

Constituent oxides	Bentonite	Attapulgitite
Oxides	Weight %	Weight %
SiO ₂	56.7	44.2
Al ₂ O ₃	15.7	11.9
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.12	4.7
CaO	4.5	10.6
MgO	3.4	4.7
Na ₂ O	1.1	0.9
K ₂ O	0.6	
SO ₃		2.3
L.O.I	9.5	15.8

2.2 Adsorbent preparation:

Four types of adsorbent Clay mineral (CM) were used in this study; CM samples were washed with tap water to remove the impurities' materials and also washed with de-ionized water that can form during activation. The washed CM was dried at 80°C for 24h in an oven to remove residual water. CM -1 Sample with will - physical activation (thermally activation) processes were carried out by dried MG in a muffle furnace ignition starting at 200°C for an hour, 400°C for another hour and finally at 600°C for three hours then kept till usage.

MG- 2 (CM/ TiO₂). CM-3 (CM/ ZnO). and CM- 4 (CM/ MoO₃) were eventually impregnated with metal oxides at (5,15 and 25%). First, metal oxides which were dissolved in an HCl solution. Then, each metal oxides solution was added to the sample of dried CM and maintained at ambient conditions for 3hr to allow the adsorbent to age and ground into small particles were activated with ignition under atmospheric air for 3hr at 600°C.

Thermal analysis: Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) technique was used to analyses thermally For CM, Kind 4000 - Perkin Elmer (USA), in Ibn-Sina Lab.(Baghdad).

2.3 Adsorption desulfurization method:

Desulfurization processes were carried out in a 100 mL flask diesel oil content of (0.954% of Sulfurs) was heated until boiling and then push a stream of air to assist the gas phase of gasoil to pass through 20cm of tubular quartz reactor, with an of internal diameter 1cm which filled with 20gm of activated CM- microparticles as adsorbent in furnace which is locally made Fig(1). Then the sweet gas-oil liquid products were recovery with a condenser and collected in a receiver flask. The side product of H₂S gas was precipitate as a yellow CdS through flask which content of CdCl₂.6H₂O solution. Processes were investigated using three temperatures (400, 500 and 550C).

2.4 Analytical methods:

The analytical methods were carried out by a Gas Chromatography (GC- FID) kind PACKARD MODEL 433A(USA). and detector kind FID, detector temperature 3000C, the temperature of the injection port 270C0, furnace temperature 100 – 300 0C and column kind SE / 30, 0 0C / min with capillary column (DB-5, 3M, diameter 1/ 8, helium (He) used as the carrier gas of samples and flow rat 20m/ min. Spectroscopic charts of GC was recorded for the studied samples. The desulfurization products were determined by XR (Thermo electronic) analyses was used to determinate the S% conversion quality control laboratory (Beji refinery).

2.5 Desulfurization tests for Nano size Clay:

The CM samples were ground and sieved by 30µm then washed with demineralized water for 2 times. Iron oxide was removed by sedimentation technique using 1M of NaOH solution under reflux for 2h at 1000C. After filtration, the solid was exposed to slow evaporation, till the dryness was obtained .

2.50g N-acetyl-N, N, Ntrimethyl ammonium bromide CTAB was selected as a surfactant to widen gallery spacing, was dissolved in 60 ml of distilled water containing 3.90×10^{-3} g mol of hydrochloric acid. The mixture was stirred under sonication at 75 0C during 30 min until a clear solution was obtained, thus indicating a perfect dissolution of an ammonium salt. 3.25 g of CM was added to the salt solution and sonication was continued for another 1 h. The precipitate formed was recovered by filtration and dispersed in hot water by mechanical stirring during 2 h the later process was repeated twice to get chloride free Nano clay. The final precipitate was thoroughly dried in an oven at 80 0C for 12 h, [14]. (AFM) Microscopy USA was used to determine for the Nano size to CM particles. Nano Clay desulfurization procedure is similar as above CM- micro particles methods of desulfurization.

3. Results and discussion:

3.1 Adsorptive desulfurization:

General three classes of absorbents (laboratory prepared) were used in this study for the desulfurization: Firstly, direct desulfurization with CM only.

Figure.1. Schematic diagram of experimental apparatus

secondly the desulfurization has been done with CM + Metal Oxide and thirdly desulfurization using Nano CM + TiO₂. All experimental carried out through the home building reactor .

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the experimental apparatus. (1-Air Pump,2-flow meter, 3 – Feeding flask of virgin Gas-oil, 4- Heater, 5- Quarts reactor, 6 –Tubular furnace, 7 – condenser, 8 – Receiver flask of Sweet Gas-oil, 9- Cadmium chloride solution for Sulfur precipitate, 10 - H₂O flask for gases dissolve. The renewability of the adsorbents was tested by carrying out repeated adsorption–thermal regeneration cycle tests. In these sets of experiments, for each adsorbent, the adsorption run was performed at a fixed condition of temperature (400,450 and 500C). The optimized temperature for high adsorption was 450C, and the best adsorbents is (Nano Attapulгите A + 25% TiO₂). The temperatures orders for the sulfurs removals were 450 °C > 400 °C > 500 0C. Results of desulfurization in Table (3- 7) by using Attapulгите – A and Bentonite – B.

Table.3 Adsorptive desulfurization using CM only.

Sample	Tempt. °C	B-CM	A-CM
Before desulfurization	R.M	0.95%	0.95%
After desulfurization	at 400 °C	0.63	0.58
	at 450 °C	0.54	0.47
	at 500 °C	0.67	0.71

Table.4 Adsorptive desulfurization results of CM+ TiO₂

CM	Tempt.C ⁰	5% TiO ₂	15% TiO ₂	25% TiO ₂	Nano + 25% TiO ₂
B	450	0.67	0.679	0.633	0.34
A	450	0.57	0.61	0.45	0.29

Table.5 Adsorptive desulfurization results of CM+ ZnO

CM	Tempt.C ⁰	5% ZnO	15% ZnO	25% ZnO
B	450	0.63	0.68	0.74
A	450	0.51	0.58	0.66

Table.6 Adsorptive desulfurization results of CM + MoO₃

CM	Tempt.C ⁰	5% MoO ₃	15% MoO ₃	25% MoO ₃
B	450	0.67	0.73	0.76
A	450	0.74	0.75	0.77

To test the effacing of the adsorbent’s catalysts for sulfur removal from gas-oil, the high capacities for these adsorbents was of (Nano A+ TiO₂) and their favorites to sulfur removal. And show mechanism which suggested for adsorption desulfurization Fig.2.and image of Nano Clay, Fig. (3-4)

Figure.2. Suggested reaction and mechanism of adsorption desulfurization

Figure.3. AFM micrographs of Nano A – CM

Figure.4. AFM micrographs of Nano B – CM

1.1.Reactivity of activated CM catalysts study:

Table.7. Show the reactivity of CM catalysts after uses several times for desulfurization at 4500C, it reduces when gasoil passes on the MG which reusing, and the S% remove was least than fresh, due to effect of high temperature and carbon accumulations, on other hand the activity of Attapulгите > Bentonite for desulfurization CM.

Table.7 Catalysts reactivity for sulfur adsorption

CM- Catalyst	Tempt.C ⁰	First pass. Sulfur % Wt	Second pass. Sulfur % Wt	Third pass. Sulfur % Wt
B	450	0.54	0.82	0.92
A	450	0.47	0.52	0.58

1.2. Gas chromatography's (GC) studies:

It is difficult to remove refractory sulfur compounds such as dibenzothiophene (DBT) and their derivatives with one or two alkyl groups which are abundant in gasoline and especially in diesel. The adsorption of dibenzothiophene (DBT) in Gas-oil onto MG has been studied by Gas chromatography through added small amount of DBT to Gas-oil and follow-up of adsorption to examine the efficiently of desulfurization process. The results show decrease of the DBT% from 5.2124 to 3.1516. Fig.5 (A,B,C,D).

Figure.5. A) GC profile for DBT (stander) dissolved with hexane.
 B) GC profile for virgin Gas-oil
 C) GC profile of adsorption Gas-oil on CM – B
 D) GC profile of adsorption Gas-oil on CM – A

1.3.TGA Study:

Thermal stability of CM has been studied and carried out with used TGA instrumental for purpose of identifying the stability through high temperatures and determination of the thermal degradation temperature, in other hand to show the optimization temperatures which will could uses of CM as catalyst in different temperatures Fig. (6). Show Bentonit at 6800C thermal degrade, Attapulgit at 725 0C which was more stable and is the best absorbent for desulfurization.

Figure.6. A) TG and DTGA Curve of CM –B
 B) TG and DTGA curve of CM- A

2. Conclusion

The results of this study indicated that the adsorption desulfurization under atmospheric condition at 400, 450 and 500°C were successfully, using natural Iraqi CM (Bentonite, Attapulgite). Adsorption efficiently was increased when impregnated with metals oxide (TiO₂, ZnO and MoO₃) with 25%, and more increased using Nano particles size of CM which managed to reduce the sulfur levels from (0.954 – 0.290). Moreover provide simple technique, cheap and ecofriendly. On other hand the efficiently of adsorption for DBT was successfully tested which showed it was bad and difficult for removal from gasoil. Efficiently of Attapulgite was favorite than Bentonit and 450°C is the optimize temperatures in the adsorption desulfurization.

References

- [1] Zhao, Y., & Wang, R., deep desulfurization of diesel oil by ultrasound-assisted catalytic ozonation combined with extraction process. *Petroleum & Coal*, 55., (2013).
- [2] Tao, H., Nakazato, T., & Sato, S., Energy-efficient ultra-deep desulfurization of kerosene based on selective photooxidation and adsorption. *Fuel*, 88(10), p.1961-1969 (2009).
- [3] Lee, J., Beum, H. T., Ko, C. H., Park, S. Y., Park, J. H., Kim, J. N., ... & Kim, S. H., Adsorptive removal of dimethyl disulfide in olefin rich C4 with ion-exchanged zeolites. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 50(10), p. 6382-6390 (2011).
- [4] Hernandez, S. P., Fino, D., & Russo, N., High performance sorbents for diesel oil desulfurization. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 65(1), p. 603-609 (2010).
- [5] Yanxiu, L., Hua, S., & Wenchao, Z., Oxidative desulfurization of model sulfur compound by potassium ferrate in the presence of phosphomolybdic acid catalyst. *China Petroleum Processing and Petrochemical Technology*, 15(1), p. 61-65. (2013).
- [6] Li, B., & Tufail, A., Direct synthesis of Ti-containing SBA-16-type mesoporous material by the evaporation-induced self-assembly metization.(2009).
- [7] Mikhail, S., Zaki, T., & Khalil, L., Desulfurization by an economically adsorption technique. *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 227(1-2), p. 265-278 (2002).
- [8] Yang, R. T., Hernández-Maldonado, A. J., & Yang, F. H., Desulfurization of transportation fuels with zeolites under ambient conditions. *Science*, 301(5629), p. 79-81 (2003).
- [9] Ma, X., Velu, S., Sun, L., Song, C., Mehdi, N., & Siva, S., Adsorptive desulfurization of JP-8 jet fuel and its light fraction over nickel-based adsorbents for fuel cell applications. In *Prepr. Symp. Am. Chem. Soc., Div. Fuel. Chem*, 48, p. 688 (2003).
- [10] Torres-garc. E, g. canizal, s. veluman., Influence of surface phenomena in oxidative desulfurization. *Appl. Phys. A* 79, p. 2037–2040 (2004).
- [11] Ma, X., Velu, S., Kim, J. H., & Song, C., Deep desulfurization of gasoline by selective adsorption over solid adsorbents and impact of analytical methods on ppm-level sulfur quantification for fuel cell applications. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 56(1-2), p. 137-147 (2005).
- [12] Wang, J., Xu, F., Xie, W. J., Mei, Z. J., Zhang, Q. Z., Cai, J., & Cai, W. M., The enhanced adsorption of dibenzothiophene onto cerium/nickel-exchanged zeolite Y. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 163(2-3), p. 538-543(2009).
- [13] Shu, C., Sun, T., Jia, J., & Lou, Z., Mild process for reductive desulfurization of diesel fuel using sodium borohydride in situ generated via sodium metaborate electroreduction. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 52(23), p. 7660-7667(2013).
- [14] Sonawane, S., Chaudhari, P., Ghodke, S., Ambade, S., Gulig, S., Mirikar, A., & Bane, A., Combined effect of ultrasound and nanoclay on adsorption of phenol. *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*, 15(6), p1033-1037(2008).